

THE INFLUENCE OF LIVE STREAMING SHOPPING AND CUSTOMER REVIEWS ON PURCHASING DECISIONS ON OVERSIZE FASHION THROUGH THE SHOPEE MARKETPLACE

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received Apr 10, 2024 Revised Apr 20, 2024 Accepted May 10, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: live streaming shopping, customer reviews, purchasing decisions, oversize fashion, Shopee marketplace.</p>	<p>Oversize fashion has become a popular trend among users of this e-commerce platform. Various types of oversized fashion products ranging from t-shirts, blouses, tunics, to dresses. Many shop users choose oversize fashion because it is easy to wear, not complicated, not tight on the body and gives a stylish and trendy impression. There is a challenge in creating a balance between style and proportion so that it still looks attractive and not too big. The purpose of this research is to examine live streaming shopping (X1) and customer reviews (X2) on purchasing decisions (Y) for oversized clothes through the Shopee marketplace. Live streaming shopping is becoming an increasingly popular marketing method due to its interativity and ability to display products directly, which helps consumers understand product details and quality. Customer reviews, as a form of previous user reviews, play an important role in building trust and providing relevant information to potential buyers. This research uses quantitative methods, this data is available through an e-questionnaire using g-from which was distributed to 130 respondents who had purchased oversized fashion through Shopee. The hypothesis was tested through multiple linear analysis. The study results show that live streaming shopping has a positive effect on purchasing decisions, showing that the more interesting and informative it is, the higher the consumer's likelihood of making a purchase. Apart from that, customer reviews were found to have a positive and relevant relationship to purchasing decisions. Positive reviews from previous customers can increase the confidence of new consumers and encourage them to make a purchase</p> <p style="text-align: right;">This is an open-access article under the CC-BY 4.0 license.</p>

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INTRODUCTION

Progress in the current era of globalization technology is developing very quickly. Communication and information technology continues to develop, one example is the

internet. As technology advances, smartphones make it easier to use the Internet, allowing people to communicate, search for information, and make purchases. And now social media has become a part of life and it cannot be denied that the presence of social media has changed society significantly. According to (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010 in (Purbohastuti WA) social media is online media that allows users to participate, share and create content, including social networks, wikis, forums and the virtual world. Social media is a group of Internet-based applications based on Web 2.0 ideology and can enable creation and exchange user-generated content."

All aspects of life, including business, are influenced by advances in science and technology, therefore many companies have changed their sales and marketing systems from traditional to modern due to current technological developments. Many businesses have set up online shops as a result of the emergence of new shopping methods such as social media. The potential for Indonesian entrepreneurs to set up online businesses is increasing. One platform that allows this to happen is Shopee, an online trading application based on a digital market. This application is known as the first platform in Indonesia to facilitate trade between consumers (C2C) via mobile devices.

There are many online shops in Indonesia, including Shopee, Tokopedia, Lazada, Blibi, Bukalapak, and many more. In this e-commerce competition map, Shopee will dominate the e-commerce market in Indonesia in 2023 based on the number of monthly visits to the market. The average monthly visits are 242.2 million, and also, Shopee is ranked first in the Appstore and Playstore (Annur MC, 2024). Shoppe presents a shopping platform that is mainly focused on mobile devices, making it easy for users to search for shopping and selling goods directly via cellphone .

One of the developing markets in Indonesia is Shoppe, and promotional programs are implemented to increase sales, including free shipping, cash, flash sales for grocery items, store reviews, customer reviews from vendors, as well as improving Shoppé services with the Live Shopping Tones feature. Shopee Live is the latest innovation from Shopee which allows sellers to sell and interact with buyers via live broadcasts on the Shopee application. (Shopee 2023). In this feature, sellers can create live broadcast sessions to promote their stores and products directly to buyers. This allows buyers to purchase products without having to leave the web page, so sellers can understand buyers' needs better and provide satisfying buying knowledge for consumers.

Shopee live is now one of the most effective promotional strategies for sellers on Shopee to market their products. Shopee live can attract hundreds of thousands of visitors every day, increasing sales up to three times, which makes it very profitable for sellers and attracts up to 15% new followers on each live session. Another Shopee feature is also Shopee Ratings where customers can provide reviews where there is an assessment or evaluation made by a customer of a product after using it or seeing whether the product is suitable or not with the product being sold by the seller.

In online purchasing, customer reviews are very important. According to (Filiari (2014) in Wahyudi et al., nd) In online sales customer reviews are a form of word of mouth communication which allows potential buyers to learn more about a product. If customers have difficulty seeing the quality of the product then there is customer information. Reviews can help other customers be decisive in making decisions. According to (Farki Ahmad, 2016) customer reviews can be an effective promotional tool

for marketing communications. This media has been used by marketers and vendors because it offers a cheap and influential channel to reach customers. Marketers are known to have used networks of influence between customers to influence the behavior of potential buyers.

The purchasing decision making process is influenced by many customer behaviors before making a purchase. Post-purchase behavior and consumer purchasing decisions do not always go through the steps necessary to purchase the product in its entirety. Smart businesses strive to fully understand how customers make purchasing decisions, including how they learn about, use, and even get rid of products. Consumers reach the point where they make a decision to buy something (Kotler & Keller, 2021: 184). Apart from that, the purchasing decision making process can also be connected to the buyer's journey. These stages are related to the marketing of a product or service, such as purchasing habits, customer decision-making processes, as well as elements that influence customer decisions (Belch & Belch, 2023).

The purchasing decision is one of the final stages in the consumer's journey when they already have the confidence and desire to buy a product. A very high level of purchasing interest often indicates a higher level of purchasing decision from the consumer. There are several oversized fashion shops on Shopee but not all shops provide the Live Streaming Shopping feature. Therefore, Live Streaming shopping can help oversized people to make it easier to find fashion references on Shopee, because Shopee Live offers a way for sellers to market their products and interact directly with customers through live shopping on the Shopee application. Through Shopee Live, customers can interact directly with sellers to get more information about Oversize Fashion and buy it without having to leave the streaming page. Customer reviews also help buyers assess the advantages and disadvantages of the product. Through promotional activities such as live streaming and customer reviews, Shopee hopes to encourage and make it easier for customers to decide to buy Oversize Fashion.

Based on the explanation of the background to the problem described above, the author is interested in conducting further research regarding "The Influence of Live Streaming Shopping and Customer Reviews on Purchasing Decisions in Oversized Fashion via the Shopee Market Place".

HYPOTHESIS

Source: Processed by the Author, 2024

1. First Hypothesis

Ho: NoThere is an influence of live streaming shopping on purchasing decisions for oversized fashion through the Shopee marketplace

- Ha: There is an influence of live streaming shopping on purchasing decisions for oversize fashion through the Shopee marketplace
2. Second Hypothesis
 Ho: NoThere is an influence of Customer Reviews on purchasing decisions for oversize fashion through the Shopee marketplace
 Ha: There is an influence of Customer Reviews on purchasing decisions for oversize fashion through the Shopee marketplace
3. Third Hypothesis
 Ho: NoThere is an influence of live streaming shopping and customer reviews on purchasing decisions for oversized fashion through the Shopee marketplace.
 Ha: There is an influence of live streaming shopping and customer reviews on purchasing decisions for oversize fashion through the Shopee marketplace.

METHODS

The aim of this research is to find out how the basic variable and the dependent variable interact significantly with each other. This research method is a quantitative approach with associative research. This research uses a probability sampling technique with purposive sampling where the sample requires certain considerations, namely meeting the criteria "consumers have purchased products twice or more at Shopee in the Surabaya area". In this research an e-questionnaire was used to collect data, and a Likert scale was used to measure. The questionnaire used is an electronic type of closed questionnaire (Closed Questionnaire). Electronic questionnaires are distributed online using Google Forms. First, the questionnaire tests the validity and reliability of the statement items. After passing, then distribute the questionnaire to obtain data. Hypothesis tests including t test (partial), f test (simultaneous) and coefficient of determination test (R2) will be used to analyze data obtained through multiple linear regression analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity test

The validity test is used to assess whether the questionnaire is valid or not. The validity of the questionnaire is determined if the calculated r exceeds the r table. Each instrument was evaluated for validity using the product moment Pearson correlation approach.

Figure 2Validity Test Results

Variabel	R Hitung	R Tabel	Kesimpulan	
<i>Live Streaming Shopping (X1)</i>	X1.1	0.562	0.349	Valid
	X1.2	0.800	0.349	Valid
	X1.3	0.742	0.349	Valid
	X1.4	0.682	0.349	Valid
	X1.5	0.609	0.349	Valid
<i>Customer Review (X2)</i>	X2.1	0.651	0.349	Valid
	X2.2	0.779	0.349	Valid
	X2.3	0.851	0.349	Valid
	X2.4	0.667	0.349	Valid
<i>Kepuasan Pembelian (X3)</i>	X3.1	0.710	0.349	Valid
	X3.2	0.789	0.349	Valid
	X3.3	0.713	0.349	Valid
	X3.4	0.665	0.349	Valid
	X3.5	0.668	0.349	Valid
	X3.6	0.527	0.349	Valid

Source: SPSS 23 Output (2024)

The results of the test above are consistent with the respondents' perceptions of each statement from the Live Streaming shopping variable (X1), Customer reviews(X2), and purchasing decisions (Y). Specifically, all calculated r values > r table from 32 respondents' answers as a validity test were greater than 0.349.

Reliability Test

Assessing the reliability of an instrument means finding out whether the instrument regularly produces the same results when reused. If the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of an instrument is more than 0.600, then the instrument is considered reliable.

Figure 3 Reliability Test Results

Variabel	Conbrach's Alpha	Angka Pembandi ng	Kesimpulan
Live Streaming Shopping (X1)	0,707	0,600	Reliabel
Customer Review (X2)	0,716	0,600	Reliabel

Source: SPSS 23 Output, (2024)

Reliability test, which describes the Cronbach's Alpha value above 0.600. This indicates that the variables Live Streaming shopping (X1), Customer reviews (X2), and purchasing decisions (Y). is considered reliable and will provide consistent results even if tested repeatedly.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 11.926 + 0.373X_1 + 0.351X_2 + e$$

- a. With a positive value of 11.926, constant (a) shows a unidirectional influence between the independent and dependent variables. Therefore, if the Live streaming Shopping (X1) and customer review (X2) variables do not change or have a constant value (0), the purchasing decision value (Y) will increase by 11.926.
- b. With a regression coefficient of 0.373. The live streaming shopping variable (X1) shows a positive influence between the purchasing decision variable (Y). Assuming the Customer review variable (X2) is equal to 0 (constant), the decision variable (Y) will increase by 0.373.
- c. With a regression coefficient of 0.377. The customer review variable (X2) shows a positive influence between the purchasing decision variable (Y). Assuming the Live streaming shopping variable (X1) is equal to 0 (Constant), the purchasing decision variable (Y) will increase by 0.377

Hypothesis testing

t Test (Partial)

To show how the independent variables sales promotion and shopping lifestyle influence the dependent variable impulse buying. A significance level of 0.05 or 5% is used to test the hypothesis.

Figure 4 t Test (Partial)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	11.926	2.225		5.359	.000
	Live Streaming Shopping	.373	.098	.321	3.812	.000
	Customer Review	.351	.107	.275	3.271	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Keputusan Pembelian

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

$T_{table} = t(a/2 ; n - k - 1)$

used to get the t table value.

Information :

a = Significance (0.05)

k = Number of independent variables

n = Number of samples used

So in this study it can be observed that the significant value (α) is 5% (0.05) with $130 - 3 = 127$, the t table is 1.978. The results of hypothesis testing are explained as follows:

1. First Hypothesis

The results of the Live Streaming Shopping test (X1) obtained a t count of 3,812 where the t count is less than the t table, namely ($3,812 > 1.978$) because the relevant level is $0.000 < 0.05$, so H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected, meaning there is an influence of Live Streaming Shopping on decisions. Purchase Oversize Fashion Through the Marketplace Shoppe..

2. Second Hypothesis

Testing From the results of the Customer Review table (X2), it is obtained that t count is 3,271 where t count < t table, namely ($3,271 > 1.978$) because the significance level is 0.001

< 0.05, then H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected, meaning that there is an influence of Customer Reviews on Purchasing Decisions On Oversize Fashion Through the Marketplace Shopee.

Simultaneous Test (F)

To find out whether the independent variables influence the dependent variable simultaneously, the F test with a significance of less than 0.05 is used. The f value in the table is smaller than the f value in the calculation.

Figure 5 Simultaneous Test (F)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	117.518	2	58.759	21.329	.000 ^b
	Residual	349.874	127	2.755		
	Total	467.392	129			

a. Dependent Variable: Keputusan Pembelian

b. Predictors: (Constant), Customer Review, Live Streaming Shopping

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

The results of the F test to find the F table are:

$$F \text{ table} = F (n - k)$$

Information :

n = Number of Samples

k = Number of Independent Variables

So :

$$= 2 ; 130 - 2$$

$$= 2 ; 128$$

$$= 3.07$$

So the calculated F table is 10.465 while the F table is 3.07. So it can be seen that F count is 21.329 > F table 3.07 and the significance value is 0.000. then it can be assessed that H_a is accepted or in other words simultaneously Live Streaming Shopping and Customer reviews influence the decision to purchase Oversize Fashion on Shopee

Coefficient of Determination Test (R²)

Figure 6 Coefficient of Determination Test (R²)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.501 ^a	.251	.240	1.660

a. Predictors: (Constant), Customer Review, Live Streaming Shopping

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

The R² (R Square) value is 0.251, which means that the influence of Live Streaming shopping and Customer Reviews on the decision to purchase Oversize Fashion at Shopee is 0.251 or 25.1%, while the remaining 74.1% is influenced by variables that have not been studied and the rest are independent variables. others who were not analyzed were (100-25.1% = 74.9%).

CONCLUSION

The discussion regarding the findings from the research explains the conclusions, including:

1. The Live Streaming Shopping variable influences the decision to purchase Oversize Fashion at Shopee, it can be concluded that it partially has a positive and significant influence. This means that by interacting with the audience, buyers can ask questions and get answers directly from the seller. Behavioral purchasing decisions when purchasing oversize fashion products on Shopee are influenced by customer reviews.
2. The Customer Review variable influences the decision to purchase Oversize Fashion at Shopee, it can be concluded that it partially has a positive and significant influence. This means that customer reviews can help reduce uncertainty regarding product quality and effectiveness through other people's experiences. This factor greatly influences consumer purchasing decisions.
3. The Live Streaming Shopping and Customer Review variables simultaneously (together) have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. This is due to the high perception of live streaming shopping and customer reviews, making it easier for consumers to make purchasing decisions about Oversize fashion

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